

Solubility of carbon dioxide in water: some useful results for hydrate nucleation

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In this paper, the solubility of carbon dioxide (CO₂) in water along the isobar of 400 bar is determined by computer simulations using the well-known TIP4P/Ice force field for water and TraPPE model for CO₂. In particular, the solubility of CO₂ in water when in contact with the CO₂ liquid phase, and the solubility of CO₂ in water when in contact with the hydrate have been determined. The solubility of CO₂ in a liquid-liquid system decreases as temperature increases. The solubility of CO₂ in a hydrate-liquid system increases with temperature. The two curves intersect at a certain temperature that determines the dissociation temperature of the hydrate at 400 bar (T_3). We compare the predictions with the T_3 obtained using the direct coexistence technique in a previous work. The results of both methods agree and we suggest 290(2) K as the value of T_3 for this system using the same cutoff distance for dispersive interactions. We also propose a novel and alternative route to evaluate the change in chemical potential for the formation of hydrate along the isobar. The new approach is based on the use of the solubility curve of CO₂ when the aqueous solution is in contact with the hydrate phase. It considers rigorously the non-ideality of the aqueous solution of CO₂, providing reliable values for driving force for nucleation of hydrates in good agreement with other thermodynamic routes used. It is shown that the driving force for hydrate nucleation at experimental conditions is higher than that for the formation of pure ice when compared at the same supercooling.

I. INTRODUCTION

At ambient conditions of temperature and pressure (298 K and 1 bar), the thermodynamically stable phase of water is the liquid phase. If the temperature is decreased at a constant pressure of 1 bar, the liquid is no longer the most stable phase and a first-order phase transition takes place at 273.15 K. Consequently, and according to the Thermodynamics laws, water must freeze. The new thermodynamically stable phase is the well-known ordinary ice, also known as Ih or hexagonal ice. This solid phase is formed by a crystalline structure characterized by the oxygen atoms forming hexagonal symmetry with nearly tetrahedral bonding angles. The same happens if the pressure is above ambient conditions up to 2100 bar, approximately. Above this pressure, water can freeze into other ices, including ice III, V, VI, among others, as the pressure is increased.¹⁻³ These are only some of the solid crystalline phases of the well-known polymorphic phases of water. However, this only happens if the original liquid phase is formed from pure water. When liquid water is mixed with another substance the story can be different.

There exist aqueous solutions of small compounds that exhibit different behavior when cooled down at constant pressure. Particularly, aqueous solutions of methane (CH₄), carbon dioxide (CO₂), nitrogen (N₂), hydrogen (H₂) or larger organic molecules, among many other different compounds, do not transform into a crystalline ice phase when the temperature is lowered. In fact, all these aqueous solutions freeze into new crystalline solid compounds named clathrate hydrates or

simply hydrates.⁴ Hydrates are non-stoichiometric crystalline inclusion compounds consisting of a network of hydrogen-bonding water molecules forming cages in which solutes (for instance, CH₄, CO₂, N₂ or H₂) are enclathrated at appropriate thermodynamic conditions of temperature and pressure.

Fundamental and applied research on hydrates and clathrates has been motivated by several reasons. First at all, hydrates are potential alternative sources of energy since huge amounts of CH₄ have been identified in hydrate deposits, either in the sea floor or in the permafrost frozen substrates, but their exploitation is not technically accessible yet due to a poor physicochemical characterization and various engineering issues.^{5,6} Another remarkably relevant aspect of hydrates from both the scientific point of view and practical interest is the possibility to capture^{7,8} and store CO₂.⁹ This places gas hydrates at the center of environmental concerns regarding atmospheric greenhouse gases. Sequestration and capture of CO₂ in hydrates constitute a technological breakthrough which is seen as a promising alternative to other conventional methodologies for CO₂ capture, such as reactive absorption using amines and selective adsorption using adsorbent porous materials including sieves and zeolites.^{10,11}

It is clear from the previous discussion that an accurate knowledge of the thermodynamics and kinetics of the formation and growth of hydrates is necessary from the fundamental and practical points of view. The thermodynamics of hydrates has been relatively well-established experimentally for years.⁴ In addition, it is also possible to describe theoretically the phase equilibria of hydrates using the van der Waals

and Platteeuw (vdW&P) formalism.^{12,13} This approach, combined with an equation of State (EOS) allows us to satisfactorily determine the phase equilibrium of both pure hydrates and mixtures.⁴ Additionally, from the point of view of molecular simulation, there has been an enormous development in techniques and methodologies for the study of the formation and dissociation of a huge variety of hydrates.^{14–21} Particularly, several research groups have determined the phase equilibrium of CO₂^{22,23} and CH₄ hydrates under oceanic crust conditions^{24,25} using the direct coexistence technique. The precise knowledge of phase equilibria of hydrates, and particularly their phase boundaries, is essential to provide a detailed description of the kinetic and nucleation processes of these systems.

Unfortunately, a complete description from a molecular perspective of the mechanisms of growth and hydrate formation is far from being satisfactory. In the last few years, some of the authors of this work have been working on the development and use of the Seeding Technique,²⁶ in combination with the Classical Nucleation Theory (CNT),²⁷ to deal with several systems including the hard-sphere and Lennard-Jones models and more complex systems such as water and salty water.²⁸ More recently, we have extended the study to deal with methane hydrates.^{29,30} It is important to recall here that Molinero and collaborators used the Seeding Technique to estimate nucleation rates of hydrates³¹ modeled through the well-known mW water model.³² Other authors have also contributed significantly to the understanding of the dynamics of nucleation and dissociation of hydrates from computer simulation.^{33–49} This work constitutes the extension of our most recent study²⁹ on methane hydrates to deal with CO₂ hydrates. Before undertaking nucleation studies of CO₂ hydrates it is necessary to account for several issues, including the solubility of CO₂ in the aqueous solution when it is in contact with the CO₂-rich liquid phase and with the hydrate, an accurate prediction of the dissociation temperature, and the driving force for the nucleation.

The fluid phase behavior of the CO₂ + water binary mixture is dominated by a large region of liquid-liquid (LL) immiscibility.^{50,51} Since the critical point of pure CO₂ is at conditions similar to those at which the CO₂ hydrates are found, between 270 – 295 K and 10 – 5000 bar, approximately, the three-phase coexistence line (i.e., a triple point that occurs at a certain temperature T_3 for each pressure) exhibits two branches. This is contrary to what happens with methane hydrates, that only exhibit one branch.⁴ At pressures below the vapor pressure of pure CO₂ (~ 30 bar), the dissociation line is a three-phase line in the PT diagram at which the hydrate, the aqueous solution of CO₂, and the gas phase of CO₂ coexist. Above the vapor pressure ($\gtrsim 40$ bar), the hydrate and the solution coexist with a CO₂ liquid phase. Both branches meet at a quadruple point at which the hydrate, aqueous solution, CO₂ liquid, and CO₂ vapor phases coexist. In this work, we concentrate on 400 bar of pressure. At these conditions, the key solubility curves in the context of nucleation of CO₂ hydrates are the solubility of CO₂ in water when the aqueous solution is in contact with the CO₂ liquid phase and with the hydrate phase. In the first case, the solubility of CO₂ increases as the temperature is de-

creased. In the second case, as it occurs for the methane hydrate, there is little or no information from computer simulations or experiments. Here we determine the solubility of CO₂ in water from the hydrate along the isobar of 400 bar. This will allow us to estimate the dissociation line of the hydrate at this pressure, as we have done in our previous work for the case of the methane hydrate.²⁹

The dissociation line of the CO₂ hydrate has been already determined by us several years ago.²² It is important to mention that also other authors have obtained similar results using computer simulations⁵² and free energy calculations.¹⁹ Our previous results are slightly different than those found by Costandy and coworkers and Waage an collaborators since unlike dispersive interactions between water and CO₂ are different. However, we follow our previous work²⁹ and determine the dissociation line of the hydrate using the solubility curve of CO₂ in the aqueous solution when it is in contact with the CO₂ liquid phase and the hydrate. We have found that the new estimations agree with the initial prediction of Míguez *et al.*²² within the corresponding uncertainties.

The formation of the CO₂ hydrate can be viewed as a chemical reaction in which water and CO₂ molecules “react” in the aqueous solution phase to form hydrate molecules.^{53–56} The change in chemical potential of this reaction is the driving force for nucleation, $\Delta\mu_N$. It is difficult to get good estimates of $\Delta\mu_N$ from experiments since it requires accurate values for a number of thermodynamic properties, including enthalpies and volumes of reactions, among other magnitudes.⁵⁴ Here we use the three independent routes introduced in our seminal paper²⁹ to deal with the nucleation driving force for the nucleation of CO₂ hydrates. In addition to this, we also propose a novel and alternative thermodynamic route based on the use of the solubility curve of CO₂ with the hydrate. This new route, that considers rigorously the non-ideality of the aqueous solution of CO₂ and provides reliable results of the driving force for nucleation, can be also used to determine $\Delta\mu_N$ of other hydrates.

The organization of this paper is as follows: In Sec. II, we describe the methodology used in this work. The results obtained, as well as their discussion, are described in Sec. III. Finally, conclusions are presented in Sec. IV.

II. METHODOLOGY

We use the GROMACS simulation package⁵⁷ to perform MD simulations. Computer simulations have been performed using three different versions of the NPT or isothermal-isobaric ensemble. For pure systems which exhibit fluid phases (pure water and pure CO₂) and aqueous solutions of CO₂ which exhibit bulk phases, we use the standard isotropic NPT ensemble, i.e., the three sides of the simulation box are changed proportionally to keep the pressure constant. For the hydrate phase, we use the anisotropic NPT ensemble in which each side of the simulation box is allowed to fluctuate independently to keep the pressure constant. This ensures that the equilibrated solid phase has no stress and that the thermodynamic properties are correctly estimated. The same ensem-

ble is used to simulate the two-phase equilibrium between the hydrate and the aqueous solution of CO₂. Finally, the two-phase equilibrium between the solution and the CO₂ liquid phase is obtained using the $NP_z\mathcal{A}T$ ensemble in which only the side of the simulation box perpendicular to the LL planar interface is allowed to change, with the interface area kept constant, to keep the pressure constant. In all simulations, we use the Verlet leapfrog⁵⁸ algorithm with a time steps of 2 fs. We use a Nosé-Hoover thermostat,⁵⁹ with a coupling time of 2 ps to keep the temperature constant. In addition to this, we also use the Parrinello-Rahman barostat⁶⁰ with a time constant equal to 2 ps to keep the pressure constant. We use two different cutoff distances for the dispersive and coulombic interactions, $r_c = 1.0$ and 1.9 nm. The water-water, CO₂-CO₂, and water-CO₂ long-range electrostatic interactions are taken into account using the particle mesh Ewald (PME) method.⁶¹ In some calculations, we also use the standard long-range corrections for the LJ part of the potential to energy and pressure with $r_c = 1.0$ nm. Water molecules are modeled using the TIP4P/Ice model⁶² and the CO₂ molecules are described using the TraPPE model.⁶³ The H₂O-CO₂ unlike dispersive energy value is given by the modified Berthelot combining rule, $\epsilon_{12} = \xi(\epsilon_{11}\epsilon_{22})^{1/2}$, with $\xi = 1.13$. This is the same used by Míguez *et al.*,²² which allows us to predict accurately the three-phase hydrate-water-carbon dioxide coexistence or dissociation line of the CO₂ hydrate, particularly the coexistence temperature at the pressure considered in this work, 400 bar (see Fig. 10 and Table II of the work of Míguez and co-workers for further details). Very recently, we have demonstrated that the same molecular parameters are able to predict accurately the CO₂ hydrate-water interfacial free energy.^{64,65}

III. RESULTS

A. Solubility of carbon dioxide in water from the CO₂ liquid phase

We first concentrate on the solubility of CO₂ in the aqueous solution when the system exhibits LL immiscibility. In this case, there exists a coexistence between the water-rich and CO₂ liquid phases. We have used the direct coexistence technique to determine the solubility of CO₂ in the aqueous solution from the CO₂ liquid phase at several temperatures along the 400 bar isobar. Particularly, we have performed MD $NP_z\mathcal{A}T$ simulations to ensure that temperature and pressure are constant. According to this, the planar interfacial area $\mathcal{A} = L_x \times L_y$ is kept constant and only L_z is varied along each simulation. Here, L_x , L_y , and L_z are the dimensions of the simulation box along the x -, y -, and z -axis, respectively. In this work, the z -axis is chosen to be perpendicular to the planar interface. The initial simulation box is prepared in the following way. We build a slab of 2800 water molecules in contact, via a planar interface, with a second slab of 1223 molecules of CO₂. The dimensions of L_x and L_y of all the simulation boxes used in this part of the work are kept constant with $L_x = L_y = 3.8$ nm. Since the pressure is constant, L_z varies along each simulation for all the temperatures considered. In

FIG. 1. Simulated equilibrium density profiles, $\rho(z)$, across the LL interface of CO₂ (continuous curves) and water (dashed curves) as obtained from MD $NP_z\mathcal{A}T$ simulations at 400 bar and 250 (black), 260 (red), 270 (blue), 280 (dark green), 290 (orange), 300 (maroon), and 310 K (green).

this work, L_z varies from 11.06 to 12.29 nm. Simulations to calculate solubilities are run during 100 ns. The first 20 ns are used to equilibrate the system and the last 80 ns are used as the production period to obtain the properties of interest. We have also determined the LL interfacial tension and details of the simulations are explained later in this section.

Figure 1 shows the density profiles of water and CO₂ as obtained by MD $NP_z\mathcal{A}T$ simulations at 400 bar and temperatures from 250 to 310 K. For a better visualization for the reader, we only plot half of the profiles corresponding to one of the interfaces exhibited by the system. The right side of the figure corresponds to the CO₂ liquid phase and the left side to the aqueous liquid phase. We divide the inhomogeneous simulation box into 200 parallel slabs along the z -direction, perpendicular to the planar LL interface, to study the density profiles. Following the standard approach, density profiles are obtained assigning the position of each interacting site to the corresponding slab and constructing the molecular density from mass balance considerations.

As can be seen, density profiles of water (dashed curves) exhibit preferential adsorption at the interface at all temperatures. Particularly, water molecules are accumulated at the aqueous phase side of the interface. The relative maximum, which is identified with the accumulation of the water molecules, increases as the temperature of the system is decreased. The bulk density of water in the aqueous solution of CO₂ (left side of the figure) slightly decreases as the temperature is lower, especially in the range of 250 – 290 K. As can be seen, density profiles of water are nearly equal to zero at the bulk CO₂ liquid phase, indicating that solubility of water in that phase is completely negligible. Míguez *et al.*⁶⁶ have previously studied the LL interface of aqueous solutions of CO₂ at similar temperatures (287 and 298 K) but at lower pressures ($P \leq 55$ bar). These authors have found similar be-

havior for the density profiles of water but with an important exception: they exhibit the traditional shape of the hyperbolic tangent function in which water density decreases monotonically from the bulk density of water in the aqueous phase to zero in the CO₂ liquid phase.

The behavior and structure of the density profiles of CO₂ (continuous curves) along the interface are similar to those exhibited by other mixtures but with an important exception: CO₂ molecules exhibit activity on both sides of the liquid-liquid interface of the system. Particularly, there is an accumulation of CO₂ molecules at the CO₂ liquid phase side of the interface. This accumulation increases as the temperature of the system is decreased, as it happens with water molecules on the other side of the interface. The bulk density of CO₂ in both phases increases as the temperature is increased. This variation is more important in the CO₂ liquid phase (right side of Fig. 1). Contrary to what happens with water density in the CO₂ phase, the density of CO₂ in the aqueous solution is not negligible. This indicates that although the solubility of CO₂ in water is small (molar fraction of CO₂ between 0.04 and 0.09 in the range 310–250 K, respectively), its value is not so low as in the case of the solubility of water in CO₂.

It is interesting to mention that density profiles of CO₂ also exhibit depressions in the aqueous solution side of the interface indicating desorption of CO₂ molecules in this region. The desorption of CO₂ molecules at the interface is correlated with the preferential adsorption of water molecules since the relative maxima and minima occur at the same position ($z \approx -0.45$ nm). Note that preferential adsorption and desorption of CO₂ molecules at the LL interface of this kind of aqueous solutions has not been previously seen in the literature. Particularly, Míguez *et al.*⁶⁶ only observe density profiles that exhibit preferential adsorption at the interface.

The solubilities of CO₂ in the aqueous phase have been determined from the information of the density profiles presented in Fig. 1 at the corresponding temperatures. Fig. 2 shows the solubilities of CO₂ along the isobar at the temperatures considered. We have also included in the figure (inset) the same results obtained previously by us corresponding to the methane + water system.²⁹ As can be seen, the solubility decreases as temperature increases. This result is in agreement with our previous work in which we considered the solubility of methane in water along the same isobar (400 bar) and in contact with the gas phase (see the inset).²⁹ In this work, the study is firstly done using a relatively short cutoff distance for dispersive interactions, $r_c = 1.0$ nm, which corresponds to a reduced cutoff value of $r^* = r_c/\sigma \approx 3.16$, with $\sigma = 0.31668$ nm. Here σ is the length scale of the Lennard-Jones intermolecular interactions associated with the water model (TIP4P/ice).⁶² In order to evaluate the effect of the cutoff distance, we have also determined the solubility of CO₂ using a larger cutoff value for the dispersive interactions (1.9 nm instead of 1.0 nm). As can be seen, the effect of increasing the cutoff is important in the whole range of temperatures considered. In particular, solubility increases between 17%, at high temperatures (310 K), and 13% at low temperatures (250 K).

We have checked that there is no a priori temperature limit to perform the simulations as the temperature is decreased.

FIG. 2. Solubility of CO₂ in the aqueous phase, as a function of temperature, at 400 bar, when the solution is in contact with the CO₂ liquid phase via a planar interface. The symbols correspond to solubility values obtained from MD $NP_z\mathcal{A}T$ simulations using a cutoff of 1.0 (green circles) and of 1.9 nm (red diamonds). Maroon squares correspond to simulation results using a cutoff of 1.0 nm and long-range corrections. Inset: solubility of methane in water, as a function of temperature, at 400 bar when the solution is in contact with the methane gas phase via a planar interface. Solubility values of methane in water are taken from our previous work.²⁹ Simulations are performed at the same conditions using a cutoff of 0.9 nm (blue triangles up) and 1.7 nm (dark green triangles down). In all cases, the curves are included as a guide to the eyes.

From this point of view, the solubility of CO₂ in the aqueous solution can be computed without any difficulty since we do not observe nucleation of the hydrate at low temperatures. This is in agreement with previous results obtained by Grabowska *et al.*²⁹ However, as the temperature is decreased the dynamics of the system slows down and the equilibration of the LL interface becomes more difficult and longer simulation runs are required to achieve equilibrated density profiles.

We have also determined the solubility using the standard long-range corrections to energy and pressure to the Lennard-Jones part of the potential (dispersive interactions). According to our results, although long-range corrections are able to improve the solubility results, differences between these results and those obtained with a cutoff of 1.9 nm are still noticeable. In particular, the solubilities predicted using this approach are underestimated between 4 and 6% along the isobar at the temperatures simulated. It is interesting to compare the behavior of the CO₂ solubility, as a function of the temperature along the 400 bar, with that corresponding to methane obtained by us previously.²⁹ As can be seen in the inset of Fig. 2, the effect of the long-range correction on the dispersive interactions is slightly larger in the case of CO₂ than in methane. This is an expected result since the CO₂ molecules are modeled using three Lennard-Jones interaction sites and methane only with one, and also because the solubility of CO₂ is about ten

times higher than the CH₄ solubility at the same thermodynamic conditions. It is also remarkable that the use of longer cutoff distances has a contrary effect on the solubility of CO₂ than in that of methane, i.e., the solubility of CO₂ increases with an increase of the cutoff whereas it decreases in the case of the solubility of methane. This is probably due to the presence of the quadrupolar moment of the CO₂ molecule and to the water–CO₂ interactions.

In the previous paragraphs, we have presented and discussed the results corresponding to the solubility of CO₂ in the aqueous solution when it is in contact with the CO₂ liquid phase. Since both phases are in contact through a planar LL interface and are in equilibrium at the same P and T , the chemical potential of water and CO₂ in both phases must satisfy that,

$$\mu_{\text{CO}_2}^I(P, T, x_{\text{CO}_2}^I) = \mu_{\text{CO}_2}^{II}(P, T, x_{\text{CO}_2}^{II}) \quad (1)$$

and

$$\mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^I(P, T, x_{\text{CO}_2}^I) = \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{II}(P, T, x_{\text{CO}_2}^{II}) \quad (2)$$

Here the superscripts I and II label the aqueous and the CO₂ liquid phases, respectively. Note that we have expressed the chemical potential of water in each phase in terms of the corresponding CO₂ molar fractions. It is important to note that this is consistent from the thermodynamic point of view and it is always possible since we are dealing with a binary system that exhibits two-phase equilibrium. Following the Gibbs phase rule, such a system has two degrees of freedom, which according to Eqs. (1) and (2) are P and T . Consequently, the thermodynamic behavior of the system is fully described solving the previous equations since the composition of water in both phases, $x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^I$ and $x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{II}$, can be readily obtained as $x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^I = 1 - x_{\text{CO}_2}^I$ and $x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{II} = 1 - x_{\text{CO}_2}^{II}$.

According to our previous results shown in Fig. 1, the density of water in the CO₂ liquid phase is $\rho_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{II} \approx 0$, and consequently, $x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{II} = \rho_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{II}/(\rho_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{II} + \rho_{\text{CO}_2}^{II}) \approx 0$ and $x_{\text{CO}_2}^{II} = 1 - x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{II} \approx 1$.

Following the approximations of the previous paragraph combined with Eq. (1), the chemical potential of CO₂ in the aqueous solution can be obtained from the chemical potential of pure CO₂ at the same P and T ,

$$\mu_{\text{CO}_2}^I(P, T, x_{\text{CO}_2}^I) \approx \mu_{\text{CO}_2}^{II}(P, T, x_{\text{CO}_2}^{II} \approx 1) \approx \mu_{\text{CO}_2}^{II}(P, T) \quad (3)$$

The chemical potential of CO₂ along the isobar can be obtained from the thermodynamic relation,

$$\left(\frac{\partial(\mu_{\text{CO}_2}/T)}{\partial T} \right)_{P, N_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}, N_{\text{CO}_2}} = -\frac{h_{\text{CO}_2}}{T^2} \quad (4)$$

where $h_{\text{CO}_2} = h_{\text{CO}_2}(P, T)$ is the partial molar enthalpy of CO₂, and the derivative is performed at constant pressure, P , and

FIG. 3. Change of chemical potential, $\Delta\mu$, as a function of temperature, of the bulk CO₂ (blue curve) and the bulk methane (green curve) obtained along the isobar 400 bar. We have arbitrarily set the value of the chemical potential of CO₂ and methane to zero at 290 and 295 K, respectively. Chemical potential values of methane are taken from our previous work.²⁹

number of water and CO₂ molecules, $N_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ and N_{CO_2} , respectively. Since in our case the CO₂ liquid phase is essentially a pure CO₂ liquid, h_{CO_2} is simply the molar enthalpy. Consequently, the chemical potential of CO₂, as a function of the temperature, along the 400 bar isobar can be obtained by integrating the Eq. (4) as,

$$\frac{\mu_{\text{CO}_2}(T)}{k_B T} = \frac{\mu_{\text{CO}_2}(T_0)}{k_B T_0} - \int_{T_0}^T \frac{h_{\text{CO}_2}(T')}{k_B T'^2} dT' \quad (5)$$

where k_B is the Boltzmann constant and T_0 is a certain reference temperature. Following our previous work²⁹, we set $\mu_{\text{CO}_2}(T_0) = 0$. According to Eq. (5), $\mu_{\text{CO}_2}(T)$ can be obtained by performing MD NPT simulations of pure CO₂ along the 400 bar isobar. In this case, since we are simulating a bulk phase, the standard NPT is used in such a way that the three dimensions of the simulation box are allowed to fluctuate isotropically. We use a cubic simulation box with 1000 CO₂ molecules. The dimensions of the simulation box, L_x , L_y , and L_z vary depending on the temperature from 3.9 to 4.2 nm. Simulations to calculate the molar enthalpy, at each temperature, are run during 100 ns, 20 ns to equilibrate the system and 80 ns as the production period to obtain h_{CO_2} . As in our previous work, we have not included the kinetic energy contribution (i.e. $5/2k_B T$ in the case of a rigid diatomic molecule such as CO₂). Note that this contribution is canceled out since we are evaluating chemical potential differences at constant P and T . In this work we choose as the reference temperature $T_0 = 290$ K. The reason for this selection will be clear later in the manuscript. Figure 3 shows the chemical potential of CO₂ as a function of the temperature (blue curve). We have also in-

cluded in the same figure the chemical potential values of the bulk methane taken from our previous work²⁹ (green curve) in order to compare both chemical potentials. Note that the reference temperature at which μ of the bulk methane is set to zero is 295 K.

B. LL interfacial free energy

From the same simulations we have also obtained the LL interfacial tension, γ , from the diagonal components of the pressure tensor. The vapour pressure corresponds to the normal component, $P \equiv P_{zz}$, of the pressure tensor. The interfacial tension is obtained using the well-known combination of the normal component and the tangential components, P_{xx} and P_{yy} through the mechanical route as,^{67–70}

$$\gamma = \frac{L_z}{2} \left[\langle P_{zz} \rangle - \frac{\langle P_{xx} \rangle + \langle P_{yy} \rangle}{2} \right] \quad (6)$$

In Eq. (6), the factor 1/2 reflects that during the simulations there exist two LL interfaces in the system, being L_z the size of the simulation box in the z direction perpendicular to the planar interface. Fig. 4 shows the LL interfacial tension value as obtained from MD $NP_z\mathcal{A}T$ simulations. Results obtained in our previous work corresponding to the LL interfacial tension of the methane + water mixture are also shown in the inset of the figure.²⁹ The interfacial tension decreases as the temperature is increased. We first calculate the interfacial tension using a cutoff value of 1.0 nm (black circles). In this case, we have used 50 ns for the equilibration period and 50 ns more for the production period in which the averages are calculated. Our results indicate that the values exhibit large fluctuations, especially at low temperatures. To improve our results, we have extended the simulations. The first 150 ns correspond to the equilibration period and the extra 150 ns are used to obtain the corresponding average values (production period). As can be seen (orange diamonds), although the mean values obtained in both cases are similar, the error bars decrease, especially at the lowest temperature.

It is well-known that the equilibrium interfacial tension value associated with an interface critically depends on the molecular details. In particular, its value is very sensitive to the cutoff due to the dispersive interactions used during the simulations.^{72–77} To account for the long-range interactions associated with the dispersive interactions, we have performed simulations using a cutoff distance of 1.9 nm, with 50 ns for equilibration and another 50 ns for production time (green circles). Note that in this case we are not using long-range corrections to energy and pressure. This value corresponds to a reduced cutoff distance $r_c^* = r_c/\sigma = 6$, which is nearly the double value used in the first set of simulations. As can be seen, the main effect of increasing the cutoff distance is to decrease the interfacial tension values. Particularly, the effect is larger at low temperatures where the difference is about 3–4 mJ/m². However, at high temperatures, differences are about 1 mJ/m².

FIG. 4. LL interfacial tension values, γ , as a function of the temperature between the CO₂ liquid phase and the aqueous solution at 400 bar obtained from MD $NP_z\mathcal{A}T$ simulations using a cutoff of 1.0 nm (black circles for 50 ns of equilibration and 50 ns of production; orange diamonds for 150 ns of equilibration and 150 ns of production) and of 1.9 nm (green circles for 50 ns of equilibration and 50 ns of production; violet triangles up for 150 ns of equilibration and 150 ns of production). Red circles correspond to simulation results using a cutoff of 1.0 nm and long-range corrections (50 ns of equilibration and 50 ns of production). The maroon square represents the experimental data taken from the literature.⁷¹ Inset: LL interfacial tension values of the methane + water mixture at 400 bar taken from our previous work.²⁹ Simulations are performed at the same pressure and similar temperature conditions using a cutoff of 0.9 nm (blue triangles up) and 1.7 nm (dark green triangles down).

In order to account for the effect of the simulation length, we have extended the simulation at 310 K. As in the other set of simulations, we have equilibrated the system during the first 150 ns and used the next 150 ns to perform the corresponding averages (violet triangles up). As can be seen, the new results are in practice identical to those obtained using only 50 ns for production time.

To be consistent with the calculations of the solubility of CO₂ in the aqueous solution, we have also determined the interfacial tension using the traditional LRC to energy and pressure. As in the previous case, we have only simulated using these corrections at 250 and 310 K (red circles). As can be seen, this approximation is not able to provide consistent results at low temperatures when compared with the data obtained using $r_c = 1.9$ nm. In particular, the interfacial tension is overestimated by more than 4.5 mJ/m², which represents more than 13% with respect to the value obtained using the larger cutoff distance. At the highest temperature, however, the overestimation of the interfacial tension is only about 0.5 mJ/m² (2%). Discrepancies at low temperatures between the results obtained using the largest cutoff distance (1.9 nm) and those using the traditional energy and pressure long-range corrections are probably due to the differences in densities in both

liquid phases at these conditions.

We have also compared the predictions obtained from MD simulations with experimental data taken from the literature (maroon squares).⁷¹ Unfortunately, to the best of our knowledge, there are no experimental data below 310K. Our results are in good agreement with experimental measurements, although we slightly overestimate it by about 6%.

Finally, it is also interesting to compare the LL interfacial tension values obtained in this work for the CO₂ + water system with those obtained in our previous work²⁹ for the methane + water binary mixture. Computer simulation values of the former system are shown in the inset of Fig. 4. As can be seen, LL interfacial tension values of the methane + water system are approximately twice than those corresponding to the mixture containing CO₂. But perhaps the most interesting feature is that, as it happens with the solubilities (see Fig. 2), an increase of the cutoff distance due to the dispersive interactions has the opposite effect in the systems which containing methane and CO₂: an increase of the cutoff distance in the CO₂ system lowers the LL interfacial tension values, while in the methane mixture the interfacial tension values increase when the cutoff is larger (blue triangles up correspond to $r_c = 0.9$ nm and dark green triangles down to $r_c = 1.7$ nm). Also note that the effect of the long-range dispersive contributions is more important in the CO₂ + water mixture than in the system containing methane. As we have discussed previously, this could be due to the presence of the electric quadrupole of CO₂.

C. Solubility of carbon dioxide in water from the hydrate phase

We have also determined the solubility of CO₂ in water when the aqueous solution is in contact with the hydrate along the 400 bar isobar at several temperatures. We first prepare a simulation box of CO₂ hydrate replicating a unit cell of hydrate four times along each spatial direction ($4 \times 4 \times 4$), using 2944 water and 512 CO₂ molecules. This corresponds to a hydrate with the cages (8 cages per unit cell) fully occupied by CO₂ molecules. We equilibrate the simulation box for 40 ns using an anisotropic barostat along the three axes. This allows the dimensions of the simulation box to change independently. The pressure is the same along the three directions and equal to 400 bar to allow the solid to relax and avoid any stress. In order to help the system to reach the equilibrium, we also prepare boxes of aqueous solutions with different concentrations of CO₂ depending on the temperature. This allows to reach the equilibrium as fast as possible in the last stage of the simulations when the hydrate and liquid phases are put in contact (see below). Particularly, we use simulation boxes of solutions containing 4000 water molecules and varying the number of CO₂ molecules depending on temperature: 50 (250, 260, and 270 K), 120 (280 and 290 K), and 240 (295 K) CO₂ molecules. We equilibrate each simulation box during 40 ns using the isothermic-isobaric or $NP_z\mathcal{A}T$ ensemble. In this case, two of the dimensions of the simulation boxes, arbitrarily named L_x and L_y , are kept constant ($L_x = L_y$

vary between 4.77 and 4.82 nm depending on the temperature) and equal to the values of two lengths of the simulation box of the hydrate. L_z is however allowed to vary to achieve the equilibrium pressure of 400 bar. Particularly, L_z varies from 10.28 to 10.53 nm depending on the temperature. Finally, the equilibrated hydrate and aqueous solution simulation boxes are assembled along the z direction sharing a planar solid-liquid interface with interfacial area $\mathcal{A} = L_x \times L_y$. We then perform simulations in the NPT ensemble using an anisotropic barostat with pressures identical in the three directions and equal to 400 bar. This allows the solid to relax and avoid any stress and obtain the correct value of the solubility at each temperature. Systems are equilibrated during 100 ns. After this, we run additional 300 ns to obtain the equilibrium density profiles of the system from 250 up to 295 K.

Fig. 5 shows the density profiles of water and CO₂ molecules as obtained from anisotropic NPT simulations at 400 bar and temperatures ranging from 250 to 295 K. The density profiles have been obtained as explained in section III.A. Note that at temperatures above 295 K it is not possible to determine the solubility because the hydrate melts. In other words, there is a kinetic limit at high temperatures to determine the solubility of CO₂ from the hydrate.

As in the case of the LL coexistence described in section III.A, we only plot half of the profiles corresponding to one of the interfaces exhibited by the system. The right side of the figure corresponds to the hydrate phase and the left side to the aqueous solution phase. The density profiles in the hydrate phase exhibit the usual solid-like behavior for water and CO₂ molecules, with peaks at the corresponding crystallographic equilibrium position at which molecules are located in the hydrate. As can be seen, the density profiles at the lowest temperatures, from 250 up to 280 K show nearly the same structure, and only small differences are observed at the hydrate-solution interface, as it is expected.

It is also interesting to analyze the behavior of profiles of water and CO₂ in the aqueous phase. The density profiles near the interface show some structural order due to the presence of the hydrate phase. Note that the positional order of the molecules is more pronounced at low temperatures, below $T \leq 280$ K. The bulk density of water (left side of the figure) slightly decreases as the temperature is increased, especially close to temperatures at which the hydrate melts. It is interesting to mention that bulk density profiles vary with temperature in the opposite way that when the aqueous solution is in contact with the CO₂ liquid phase (see Fig. 1).

The bulk density of CO₂ (in the aqueous solution phase) increases as the temperature is increased. From the inspection of Fig. 5 it is clearly seen that the hydrate phase becomes less stable as the temperature approaches to 290 – 295 K. At lower temperatures, the hydrate-solution interface is located at $z \approx 5$ nm, approximately, with the hydrate phase showing 6 – 7 well-defined CO₂ layers. However, at 290 and 295 K only 5 – 6 layers can be observed in the hydrate phase, with the interface located at $z \approx 6$ nm. In fact, as we have previously mentioned, it is not possible to keep stable the hydrate at temperatures above 295 K, which eventually melts at higher temperatures.

FIG. 5. Simulated equilibrium density profiles, $\rho(z)$, across the hydrate–CO₂ liquid interface, of CO₂ (continuous curves) and water (dashed curves) as obtained from MD anisotropic *NPT* simulations at 400 bar and 250 (black), 260 (red), 270 (blue), 280 (dark green), 290 (orange), and 295 K (green).

We have calculated, from the information obtained from the density profiles, the solubility of CO₂ in the aqueous solution when it is in contact with the hydrate. As can be seen in Fig. 6, the solubility of CO₂ increases as the temperature is raised. We have also included in Fig. 6 (inset) the same results obtained previously by us corresponding to the methane + water system.²⁹ It can be seen that our results are in agreement with the results of the solubility of methane. Contrary to what happens in the case of the methane hydrate, it is only possible to calculate the solubility up to a temperature of 295 K. This is just a few degrees (around five) above the values of the three point temperature T_3 of the CO₂ hydrate at this pressure (see section III.D). In the case of our previous work, the hydrate was kept in metastable equilibrium at about 35 K over the dissociation temperature of the methane hydrate (295 K).²⁹

We have also considered the impact of using different cutoff distances on solubilities. As in the case of the results presented in Section III.A, we have used three different cutoff distances for the dispersive interactions. Particularly, we use the same two values, 1.0 and 1.9 nm. We have also performed simulations using the standard long-range corrections to energy and pressure with a cutoff value of 1.0 nm. Contrary to what happens with the solubility of CO₂ in water when the solution is in contact with the other liquid phase (CO₂), the solubility does not depend on the cutoff distance, as can be seen in Fig. 6. Our results indicate that the long-range corrections due to the dispersive interactions have little or negligible effect on solubilities in aqueous solutions in contact with the hydrate. However, according to Figs. 2 and 4, long-range interactions play a key role in the thermodynamic and interfacial properties in systems involving fluid phases.^{72–77}

Finally, it is important to remark that, contrary to what we have found in our previous work for the solubility of methane in water,²⁹ we do not find a melting of the hydrate in a two-

FIG. 6. Solubility of CO₂ in the aqueous phase, as a function of temperature, at 400 bar, when the solution is in contact with the hydrate phase via a planar interface. The symbols correspond to solubility values obtained from MD anisotropic *NPT* simulations using a cutoff of 1.0 (blue circles) and of 1.9 nm (dark green diamonds). Orange squares correspond to simulation results using a cutoff of 1.0 nm and long-range corrections. Inset: solubility of methane in water, as a function of temperature, at 400 bar when the solution is in contact with the hydrate phase via a planar interface. Solubility values of methane in water are taken from our previous work.²⁹ Simulations are performed at the same conditions using a cutoff of 0.9 nm (blue triangles up) and 1.7 nm (dark green triangles down). In all cases, the curves are included as a guide to the eyes.

step process, i.e., a bubble of pure methane appears in the liquid phase as a first step and then the methane of the aqueous solution moves to the bubble and the methane from the hydrate moves to the aqueous solution as a second step. We find here that the hydrogen bonds of the layer of the hydrate in contact with the aqueous solutions break and the hydrate starts to melt.

D. Three-phases coexistence from solubility calculations

We have obtained the solubility of CO₂ in the aqueous solution, as a function of the temperature at a fixed pressure of 400 bar, when it is in contact with the CO₂ liquid phase (Section III.A) and with the hydrate (Section III.C). In both cases, the system exhibits two-phase coexistence. It is interesting to represent both solubilities in the same plot as we did in our previous study,²⁹ and as it is shown in Fig. 7. Since one of the solubility curves is a decreasing function of the temperature and the other an increasing function of the temperature, there exists a certain temperature, that we will call T_3 for reasons that will be clear soon, at which both solubilities are equal at 400 bar.

The points of the solubility curve of CO₂ in the aqueous solution from the CO₂ liquid phase correspond to thermody-

amic states at which the pressure and the chemical potentials of water and CO₂ in the aqueous phase are equal to those in the CO₂ liquid phase. In addition to this, the points of the solubility of CO₂ in water from the hydrate phase correspond to states at which the pressure is also the same and at which the chemical potentials of both components in the aqueous phase are equal to those in the hydrate phase. Consequently, at T_3 , the temperature, pressure, and chemical potentials of water and CO₂ in the aqueous solution, CO₂ liquid, and hydrate phases are the same. This means that the point at which the two solubility curves cross represents a three-phase coexistence state of the system at 400 bar. This is also known as the dissociation temperature of the CO₂ hydrate at the corresponding pressure (400 bar).

The value obtained in this work for the T_3 is 290(2) K. We assume here an uncertainty of 2 K for the dissociation temperature of the hydrate, following the same estimation of the T_3 error of the methane hydrate determined in our previous work.²⁹ The dissociation temperature result is in good agreement (within the corresponding uncertainties) with the value obtained by Míguez *et al.* using the direct coexistence technique,²² 287(2) K. It is important to remark here that we are using the same models for water (TIP4P/ice)⁶² and CO₂ (TraPPE),⁶³ the same unlike dispersive interactions ($r_c = 1.0$ nm) than in the work of Míguez *et al.*²² At this point it is important to remark that the system sizes of this work are different than that used in the work of Míguez *et al.*,²² and this could have a subtle effect in the T_3 because of finite-size effects, as it has been found for the melting point of ice Ih.⁷⁸

Other authors have determined the T_3 for this system from computer simulation. Costandy *et al.*⁵² have calculated the dissociation temperature of the CO₂ hydrate at 400 bar using the direct coexistence technique. They obtained a value of 283.5(1.7) K. Although they also used the same water and CO₂ models, a number of differences lead to a slightly different value of T_3 : different unlike dispersive interactions between water and CO₂ and cutoff distance for dispersive interaction (1.1 nm). Waage and collaborators¹⁹ have also determined the dissociation line of the hydrate using free energy calculations. They also use the same models for water and CO₂ but different unlike dispersive interactions between them. In this case, the cutoff distance for dispersive interactions is $r_c = 1.0$ nm. These authors calculate the dissociation temperature of the hydrate at 200 and 500 bar. The values obtained are 293.9(1.7) and 284.8(0.9) K, respectively. Interpolating to 400 bar, the T_3 is 284.5 K, in good agreement with the results of Costandy *et al.*⁵² Unfortunately, the result obtained here can not be compared with the predictions of Costandy *et al.*⁵² and Waage and collaborators¹⁹ since dispersive interactions are not the same as those used here.

Finally, it is important to focus on the effect of the cutoff distance used to evaluate the long-range dispersive interactions. The T_3 value of 290(2) K has been obtained using a cutoff distance of 1.0 nm. We have also analyzed the solubilities of CO₂ from the CO₂ liquid and the hydrate phases using a much larger cutoff distance (i.e., 1.9 nm). As we have previ-

ously shown, the solubility of CO₂ from the CO₂ liquid phase increases when the value of the cutoff is increased. On the other hand, the solubility of CO₂ in the hydrate phase is not affected by the use of larger cutoff values. Consequently, the combined effect of the increase of the cutoff distance of the dispersive interactions is an increase of the T_3 since it is the intersection of the two solubility curves shown in Fig. 7. Particularly, the dissociation temperature of the hydrate is now found at 292(2) K, 2 K above the T_3 observed with a cutoff distance of 1.0 nm, approximately.

It is interesting to compare the effect of the cutoff due to the dispersive interaction in both CO₂ and methane hydrates. As can be seen, in the case of the methane hydrate, T_3 is shifted towards lower temperatures, by 2 K, when the cutoff is increased. In the current case (CO₂ hydrate), we observed the opposite effect, i.e., T_3 increases when the cutoff distance is increased. This is the same effect as observed for the solubility curve of CO₂ in the aqueous solution in contact with the CO₂ liquid phase. This effect, contrary to that observed in the methane hydrate, could be due to the electrostatic interactions of the quadrupole of CO₂ with other CO₂ molecules and also with water molecules, that it is not present in the case of the methane. We think this issue deserves a more detailed study but this is out of the scope of the current work.

We have determined the dissociation line of the CO₂ hydrate at 400 bar from the calculation of the solubility of CO₂ when the aqueous solution is in contact with the other two phases in equilibrium, the CO₂ liquid phase and the hydrate phase. Grabowska and collaborators²⁹ have already demonstrated that this route allows to determine T_3 of hydrates. This work confirms that this methodology is a good alternative to the direct coexistence method. Particularly, it shows a slightly better efficiency compared with the other technique (lesser simulation times are required) and provides consistent values of T_3 .

E. Driving force for nucleation of hydrates

The dissociation line of the CO₂ hydrate separates its phase diagram in two parts in which two different two-phase coexistence regions exist.⁴ At a certain pressure, for instance, 400 bar, at temperatures above T_3 the system exhibits LL immiscibility between an aqueous solution and a CO₂ liquid phase. Note that the solubility of water in CO₂ is very small and the CO₂ liquid phase can be considered pure CO₂ in practice. However, at temperatures below T_3 the system exhibits SL phase equilibrium between the hydrate and a fluid phase (water or CO₂ depending on the global composition of the system). This is consistent with the nature of the dissociation or three-phase line at which the hydrate, aqueous solution, and CO₂ liquid phases coexist.

The fluid phase in equilibria with the hydrate below T_3 depends on the global composition of the system. Here we assume that the hydrate is fully occupied by CO₂ molecules, i.e., 8 CO₂ molecules for every 46 water molecules according to the stoichiometry of hydrates type sI. Let be $N_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ and N_{CO_2} the number of water and CO₂ molecules used in the

FIG. 7. Solubilities of CO_2 from the CO_2 liquid and the hydrate along the isobar $P = 400$ bar. The crossing of the two curves determines the dissociation temperature of the hydrate, T_3 , at 400 bar. The symbols and colors are the same as those in Figs. 2 and 6. Inset: solubilities of methane from the gas and the hydrate phase, as a function of temperature, at 400 bar. Solubility values of methane in water are taken from our previous work.²⁹ Simulations are performed at the same conditions using a cutoff of 0.9 nm (black curves) and 1.7 nm (violet curves). In all cases, the curves are included as a guide to the eyes.

fluid phases during the simulations, respectively. If the ratio $N_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}/N_{\text{CO}_2} > 5.75$, one should have hydrate–water phase separation (below T_3). However, if $N_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}/N_{\text{CO}_2} < 5.75$, one should have a hydrate – CO_2 phase system for $T < T_3$.

As described by Kashchiev and Firoozabadi⁵⁴ and Grabowska and collaborators,²⁹ the formation of a hydrate in the aqueous solution phase can be viewed as a chemical reaction that takes place at constant P and T ,

Since we are work at constant pressure in this work ($P = 400$ bar), we drop the dependence of P in the rest of equations. Assuming that all the cages of the hydrate are filled, a unit cell of CO_2 hydrate is formed by 46 water molecules and 8 CO_2 molecules, i.e., 1 CO_2 molecule per $46/8 = 5.75$ water molecules. According to this, Eq. (7) considers the hydrate as a new compound formed from one molecule of CO_2 and 5.75 molecules of water. We can also associate to this compound one unique chemical potential for the hydrate at T , $\mu_{\text{H}}^{\text{H}}(T)$. Note that this chemical potential is simply the sum of the chemical potential of CO_2 in the solid plus 5.75 times the chemical potential of water in the solid, i.e.,

$$\mu_{\text{H}}^{\text{H}}(T) = \mu_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{H}}(T) + 5.75 \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{H}}(T) \quad (8)$$

According to the previous discussion, the compound

$[\text{CO}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{5.75}]_{\text{H}}$ is simply the “hydrate” and we call one “molecule” of the hydrate in the solid the molecule $[\text{CO}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{5.75}]$.

Following Kashchiev and Firoozabadi,⁵⁴ we denote the driving force for nucleation of the hydrate formed from the aqueous solution with a concentration x_{CO_2} at T as,

$$\Delta\mu_{\text{N}}(T, x_{\text{CO}_2}) = \mu_{\text{H}}^{\text{H}}(T) - \mu_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}}(T, x_{\text{CO}_2}) - 5.75 \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{aq}}(T, x_{\text{CO}_2}) \quad (9)$$

Note that $\Delta\mu_{\text{N}}$ in this paper is $\Delta\mu_{\text{nucleation}}$ in our previous paper.²⁹ $\mu_{\text{H}}^{\text{H}}(T)$ has been previously defined in Eq. (8) as the chemical potential of the “hydrate molecule” in the hydrate phase, and $\mu_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}}(T, x_{\text{CO}_2})$ and $\mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{aq}}(T, x_{\text{CO}_2})$ are the chemical potentials of CO_2 and water in the aqueous solution, respectively, at T and molar fraction of CO_2 , x_{CO_2} . Note that the composition of CO_2 in Eq. (9) is, a priori, independent of the pressure and temperature selected. In other words, one could have different driving forces for nucleation, at a given P and T , changing the composition of the aqueous solution (for instance, in a supersaturated solution of CO_2). However, there exists a particular value of x_{CO_2} which is of great interest from the experimental point of view. Experiments on the nucleation of hydrates are performed when the water phase is in contact with the CO_2 liquid phase through a planar interface. Since both phases are in equilibrium at P and T , the solubility of CO_2 in water (molar fraction of CO_2 in the aqueous solution) is fully determined since $x_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{eq}} \equiv x_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{eq}}(T)$. Following the notation of Grabowska and coworkers,²⁹ the driving force for nucleation at experimental conditions is given by,

$$\Delta\mu_{\text{N}}^{\text{EC}}(T) = \mu_{\text{H}}^{\text{H}}(T) - \mu_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}}(T, x_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{eq}}(T)) - 5.75 \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{aq}}(T, x_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{eq}}(T)) \quad (10)$$

Note that $\Delta\mu_{\text{N}}^{\text{EC}}$ depends only on T (and on P but in this work we are working at the same $P = 400$ bar). We provide here valuable information for this magnitude when the molecules are described using the TIP4P/Ice and TraPPE models for water and CO_2 , respectively.

In the next sections we concentrate on the driving force for nucleation at experimental conditions, $\Delta\mu_{\text{N}}^{\text{EC}}(T)$, obtained using four different routes. In the first one (route 1), we use the definition of the driving force of nucleation given by Eq. (10). In the second one (route 2), we use the solubility curves of CO_2 from the hydrate and the CO_2 liquid phase. In third one (route 3), we use the enthalpy of dissociation of the hydrate and assume that it does not change with temperature nor composition. In the fourth one (route 4), we propose a novel methodology based on the use of the solubility curve of CO_2 with the hydrate, valid not only for the CO_2 hydrate but also for other hydrates. Finally, we discuss the results obtained using the different routes and compare the driving force for nucleation of the CO_2 hydrate with that of the methane hydrate previously obtained by us in a previous work.³⁰

1. Route 1 for calculating $\Delta\mu_N^{EC}$.

Route 1 was proposed and described in our previous work²⁹ and we summarize here only the main approximations and the final expression of the driving force for nucleation. To evaluate $\Delta\mu_N^{EC}(T, x_{CO_2}^{eq})$ in Eq. (10) we need to calculate the chemical potential of the “hydrate molecule” in the hydrate phase, and the chemical potentials of CO₂ and water in the aqueous phase at a supercooled temperature T below T_3 . The change in the hydrate chemical potential when the temperature passes from T_3 to T can be evaluated in a similar way than that for pure CO₂ from T_3 to T . In fact, this later change has been already calculated in Section III.A using Eq. (5) and evaluated from the corresponding thermodynamic integration using computer simulations in the NPT ensemble.

The chemical potential of water in the aqueous phase at T can be estimated using the procedure of Grabowska and collaborators²⁹ applied to the case of the CO₂ hydrate according

$$\frac{\Delta\mu_N^{EC}(T, x_{CO_2}^{eq})}{k_B T} = - \int_{T_3}^T \frac{h_H^H(T') - \{h_{CO_2}^{pure}(T') + 5.75h_{H_2O}^{pure}(T')\}}{k_B T'^2} dT' - [k_B T \ln\{x_{CO_2}^{eq}(T)\} - k_B T_3 \ln\{x_{CO_2}^{eq}(T_3)\}] \quad (11)$$

Note that it is necessary to use that the driving force for nucleation at T_3 is equal to zero, i.e.,

$$\Delta\mu_N^{EC}(T_3, x_{CO_2}^{eq}) = \mu_H^H(T_3) - \mu_{CO_2}^{aq}(T_3, x_{CO_2}^{eq}(T_3)) - 5.75 \mu_{H_2O}^{aq}(T_3, x_{CO_2}^{eq}(T_3)) = 0 \quad (12)$$

This is equivalent to arbitrary equal to zero the chemical potentials of the hydrate, CO₂, and water at T_3 .

As we have previously mentioned, each change in the chemical potentials needed to compute the driving force for nucleation is obtained by evaluating molar enthalpies of pure CO₂, water, and hydrate phases involved in the integrals given by Eq. (11). Note that the chemical potential of CO₂ in the aqueous solution has been already obtained in Section III.A. Particularly since the solubility of water in the CO₂ liquid phase is extremely low, the chemical potential of CO₂ in the aqueous solution is equal to that of pure CO₂ at the same P and T . Consequently, it has been obtained from the integration of the molar enthalpy at several temperatures according to Eq. (5).

In the case of water, the chemical potential can be obtained performing MD NPT simulations of pure water along the 400bar isobar. As in the case of pure CO₂, we also use the standard NPT is used in such a way that the three dimensions of the simulation box are allowed to fluctuate isotropically. We used a cubic simulation box with 1000 H₂O molecules. The dimensions of the simulation box, L_x , L_y , and L_z vary depending on the temperature from 3.14 to 3.08 nm. Simulations to calculate the molar enthalpy, at each temperature, are run during 100ns, 20ns to equilibrate the system, and 80ns as the production period to obtain $h_{H_2O}^{pure}$.

to Eqs. (20)-(26) of their paper. This is done in two steps. In the first step, the change in the chemical potential of the solution when its temperature passes from T to T_3 is approximated by that of pure water calculated from thermodynamic integration (see Eqs. (24) and (26) of the work of Grabowska and collaborators). The second step involves the change in the chemical potential of the solution when the composition of CO₂ changes from $x_{CO_2}^{eq}(T_3)$ to $x_{CO_2}^{eq}(T)$ (see Eq. (25) of our previous work). The rigorous calculation of this contribution requires the knowledge of the activity coefficient of water in an aqueous solution with a given composition of CO₂, $\gamma_{H_2O}^{aq}(T, x_{CO_2}^{eq})$, at T and T_3 . Grabowska and coworkers assume that this magnitude, in the case of an aqueous solution of methane, $\gamma_{H_2O}^{aq}(T, x_{H_2O}^{eq}) \approx 1$ since the solution is very diluted. We follow in route 1 the same assumption.

Using these approximations it is possible to compute the driving force at experimental conditions for nucleation given by Eq. (10). The final expression is given by,

In the case of the pure hydrate, we have obtained the chemical potential in a similar way, performing simulations in the NPT ensemble using an anisotropic barostat, i.e., the pressure is fixed at 400bar but each dimension of the simulation box is allowed to fluctuate independently. This ensures the absence of any stress in the equilibrated solid phase. At the beginning of each simulation, we use a cubic box formed by 27 replicas of the unit cell in a $3 \times 3 \times 3$ geometry. The dimensions of the simulation box vary between 3.85 and 3.62nm depending on the temperature. As in the rest of simulations, we calculate the enthalpy at different temperatures, from 260 to 295K. Simulations are run during 100ns, 20ns to equilibrate the system and 80ns to calculate the molar enthalpy of the hydrate.

2. Route 2 for calculating $\Delta\mu_N^{EC}$.

Route 2 was also proposed and described in our previous work²⁹. This route is inspired by the work of Molinero and coworkers³¹ and we summarize here only the main approximations and the final expression of the driving force for nucleation. According to this, it is possible to find a different, but an equivalent, thermodynamic route to calculate the driving force for the nucleation of methane hydrates. We check in this work whether this approach can also be used to deal with CO₂ hydrates. Let us consider Eq. (10) at experimental conditions, i.e., at the equilibrium composition of CO₂ in the aqueous solution when it is in contact via a planar interface with a CO₂ liquid phase (L), $x_{CO_2}^{eq}(P, T|L)$. Note that the vertical line represents flat interface equilibrium with the liquid CO₂. To clarify the derivation of the final expression, we write explicitly

the solubility of water in the solution, at experimental conditions, as $x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{eq}}(P, T|\text{L})$. Obviously, as we have mentioned previously in Section III.A, the solubility of water in the solution can be obtained readily as $x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{eq}}(P, T|\text{L}) = 1 - x_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{eq}}(P, T|\text{L})$.

We now assume that the chemical potential of the ideal solution's components can be expressed, in general, in terms of the chemical potentials of the pure components in the standard state and their molar fractions. In other words, since the composition of CO_2 in the solution is small, we are assuming that water is the dominant component (solvent) and the CO_2 is the minor component (solute) in the mixture. Under these circumstances, the activity coefficients of water and CO_2 are close to one.⁷⁹ According to this and following our previous work,²⁹ Eq. (10) can be written as,

$$\Delta\mu_{\text{N}}^{\text{EC}}(T) = -k_{\text{B}}T \ln \left[\frac{x_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{eq}}(T|\text{L})}{x_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{eq}}(T|\text{H})} \right] - 5.75k_{\text{B}}T \ln \left[\frac{x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{eq}}(T|\text{L})}{x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{eq}}(T|\text{H})} \right] \quad (13)$$

$x_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{eq}}(T|\text{H})$ and $x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{eq}}(T|\text{H})$ represent the molar fraction of CO_2 and H_2O in the solution when it is in contact via a planar interface (vertical line) with the hydrate phase (H), respectively. This is the equation obtained previously by us considering the driving force for the nucleation of the methane hydrate.²⁹ As we will see later in this section, Eq. (13) does not provide reliable values for the driving force of nucleation of the CO_2 hydrate, contrary to what happens with the methane hydrate. In this former case, the solubilities of methane in the solution when is in contact with the methane phase and with the hydrate are one order of magnitude lower with than those of CO_2 in the case of the CO_2 hydrate. Consequently, this route can be useful only in cases in which the solubility of the guest is extremely low.

3. Route 3 (dissociation) for calculating $\Delta\mu_{\text{N}}^{\text{EC}}$.

It is possible to estimate the driving force for nucleation of a hydrate using a simple and approximate route based on the knowledge of the enthalpy of dissociation of the hydrate.⁵⁴ The dissociation enthalpy of the hydrate, $h_{\text{H}}^{\text{diss}}$, is defined as the enthalpy change of the process,²⁹

Dissociation enthalpies are usually calculated assuming that the hydrate dissociates into pure water and pure CO_2 . Note that this corresponds to the definition of enthalpy of dissociation and that in reality CO_2 will be dissolved in water and an even smaller amount of water will be dissolved in the CO_2 liquid phase. We have determined the dissociation enthalpy of the hydrate simply by performing simulations of the pure phases (hydrate, water, and CO_2) at several temperatures at 400 bar.

According to our previous work,²⁹ we evaluate the driving force for nucleation assuming the following approximations: (1) the enthalpy of dissociation of the hydrate, $h_{\text{H}}^{\text{diss}}$ does not change with the temperature; (2) its value can be taken from its value at T_3 ; and (3) enthalpy of dissociation does not vary with composition of the aqueous solution containing CO_2 when the temperature is changed. According to this, $\Delta\mu_{\text{N}}^{\text{EC}}$ is given by,

$$\Delta\mu_{\text{N}}^{\text{EC}} = k_{\text{B}}T \int_{T_3}^T \frac{h_{\text{H}}^{\text{diss}}}{k_{\text{B}}T'^2} dT' \approx -h_{\text{H}}^{\text{diss}}(T_3) \left(1 - \frac{T}{T_3}\right) \quad (15)$$

4. Route 4 for calculating $\Delta\mu_{\text{N}}^{\text{EC}}$.

The driving force for nucleation of the CO_2 hydrate, at any arbitrary temperature, T_{N} , and molar fraction of CO_2 in the aqueous solution, $x_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{(N)}}$, at fixed pressure is defined as,

$$\Delta\mu_{\text{N}}(T_{\text{N}}, x_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{(N)}}) = \mu_{\text{H}}^{\text{H}}(T_{\text{N}}) - \mu_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}}(T_{\text{N}}, x_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{(N)}}) - 5.75\mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{aq}}(T_{\text{N}}, x_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{(N)}}) \quad (16)$$

Note that $\Delta\mu_{\text{N}}$ also depends on pressure. However, since we are work at constant pressure ($P = 400$ bar), we drop the pressure dependence from equations from this point. It is also important to recall that since we are assuming that all cages of the hydrate are filled, the chemical potential of a ‘‘hydrate molecule’’ in the hydrate phase depends only on temperature. Finally, the chemical potentials of CO_2 and water also depend on the molar fraction of water in the aqueous solution, $x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{N}}$. Since we are dealing with a binary mixture, $x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{N}} = 1 - x_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{N}}$. For simplicity, we choose $x_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{N}}$ as independent variable of the chemical potentials of CO_2 and water in the solution.

The driving force for nucleation of the CO_2 hydrate, $\Delta\mu_{\text{N}}$, depends on T_{N} and $x_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{N}}$ and both are independent variables. This means that route 4 is valid for calculating the driving force for nucleation at any T_{N} and $x_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{N}}$. As we will see later, the method can be particularized to evaluate $\Delta\mu_{\text{N}}$ at experimental conditions. In this case, $\Delta\mu_{\text{N}} = \Delta\mu_{\text{N}}^{\text{EC}}(T_{\text{N}}) = \Delta\mu_{\text{N}}^{\text{EC}}(T_{\text{N}}, x_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{eq}}(T_{\text{N}}))$, as we have previously mentioned.

To evaluate $\Delta\mu_{\text{N}}$ we need to calculate the chemical potential of the ‘‘hydrate molecule’’, $\mu_{\text{H}}^{\text{H}}(T_{\text{N}})$, at a supercooled temperature T_{N} , and the chemical potentials of CO_2 and water molecules of an aqueous solution of CO_2 with molar fraction $x_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{N}}$ at the same temperature. This route is based on the use of the solubility curve of the hydrate with temperature, at constant pressure, previously described in Section III.C. A schematic depiction of the curve and the thermodynamic route for obtaining $\Delta\mu_{\text{N}}$ at arbitrary T_{N} and $x_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{N}}$ is presented in Fig. 8. Let us consider a reference state in our calculations at temperature T_{ref} on the solubility curve in contact with the hydrate. As it will be clear later, the particular value of T_{ref} is not important since we are dealing with differences of chemical potentials and the final value of $\Delta\mu_{\text{N}}$ does not depend on the election of the reference state.

FIG. 8. Schematic depiction of route 4 for obtaining $\Delta\mu_N$. The blue solid curve represents the solubility curve of CO_2 with the hydrate (hydrate–solution equilibrium). The red square represents a reference state (ref) at T_{ref} , the green square is a state at T_i at which the aqueous solution with molar fraction $x_{\text{CO}_2}^N$ is in equilibrium with the hydrate phase, and the magenta diamond the state at T_N and $x_{\text{CO}_2}^N$ at which $\Delta\mu_N$ is calculated. The arrows in colors represent the paths followed by thermodynamic integration using Eqs. (18) (red arrow), (22) (blue arrow), and (25) (green arrow).

The first contribution to $\Delta\mu_N$ in Eq. (16) is the chemical potential of the “hydrate molecule” in the hydrate phase at T_N . The chemical potential μ_H^H can be obtained using the Gibbs-Helmholtz thermodynamic relation for pure systems,

$$\left(\frac{\partial(\mu_H^H/T)}{\partial T}\right)_{P, N_H} = -\frac{h_H^H}{T^2} \quad (17)$$

where $h_H^H = h_H^H(T)$ is the molar enthalpy of the “hydrate molecule” and the derivative is performed at constant pressure, P , and number of “hydrate molecules”, N_H . The chemical potential of the “hydrate molecule” in the hydrate phase at a supercooling temperature T_N can be obtained by integrating the Eq. (17) from T_{ref} to T_N as,

$$\frac{\mu_H^H(T_N)}{k_B T_N} = \frac{\mu_H^H(T_{ref})}{k_B T_{ref}} - \int_{T_{ref}}^{T_N} \frac{\mu_H^H(T)}{k_B T^2} dT \quad (18)$$

where k_B is the Boltzmann constant.

The last two contributions to the driving force for nucleation in Eq. (16), $\mu_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}}$ and $\mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{aq}}$, need to be evaluated at temperature T_N and molar fraction $x_{\text{CO}_2}^N$. Individual chemical potentials of CO_2 and water in the solution at a given temperature are not easy to evaluate, as we have seen in routes 1 and 2. However, it is possible to use the solubility curve of CO_2 with the hydrate to overcome this problem.

Let be T_i the temperature at which the aqueous solution with molar fraction $x_{\text{CO}_2}^N$ is in equilibrium with the hydrate phase

as indicated in Fig. 8. Since both phases are in equilibrium at these conditions, the chemical potentials of CO_2 and water in the hydrate phase and in the aqueous solution are equal,

$$\mu_{\text{CO}_2}^H(T_i) = \mu_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}}(T_i, x_{\text{CO}_2}^N) \quad (19)$$

$$\mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^H(T_i) = \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{aq}}(T_i, x_{\text{CO}_2}^N) \quad (20)$$

Note that $x_{\text{CO}_2}^N = x_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{eq}}(T_i | H)$ according to the nomenclature used in Section III.E.2 (route 2) and in our previous paper.²⁹ The vertical lines here represent that the aqueous solution is in equilibrium with the solid hydrate via a flat interface.

Combining Eqs. (19) and (20) with Eq. (8), that gives the chemical potential of the “hydrate molecule” in terms of the chemical potentials of CO_2 and water in the hydrate phase, we obtain,

$$\mu_H^H(T_i) = \mu_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}}(T_i, x_{\text{CO}_2}^N) + 5.75 \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{aq}}(T_i, x_{\text{CO}_2}^N) \quad (21)$$

Eq. (21) is the heart of route 4. According to it, the combination $\mu_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}} + 5.75 \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{aq}}$ is known along the solubility curve of the hydrate at any temperature T_i : it is equal to the chemical potential of the “hydrate molecule” at the temperature considered. This apparently simple result allows to calculate accurately the driving force for nucleation at any temperature and composition of the solution using a two-steps thermodynamic integration. As it will be clear at the end of this section, this method can be used to determine the driving force for nucleation of other hydrates.

In the first step, we calculate the difference of $\mu_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}} + 5.75 \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{aq}}$ between the reference state (ref) at T_{ref} and a second state (i) at T_i , both on the solubility curve of CO_2 with the hydrate as indicated in Fig 8. According to Eq. (21), this is completely equivalent to evaluate the difference of μ_H^H between T_{ref} and T_i along the solubility curve. This change can be evaluated using again the Eq. (17) (Gibbs-Helmholtz relation) and integrating between the two temperatures,

$$\frac{\mu_H^H(T_i)}{k_B T_i} = \frac{\mu_H^H(T_{ref})}{k_B T_{ref}} - \int_{T_{ref}}^{T_i} \frac{\mu_H^H(T)}{k_B T^2} dT \quad (22)$$

In the second step, that involves the difference between the chemical potentials of CO_2 and water in solution at temperatures T_i and T at constant molar fraction $x_{\text{CO}_2}^N$, $\Delta\mu_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}}$ and $\Delta\mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{aq}}$, can be obtained from the Gibbs-Helmholtz equation for CO_2 and water,

$$\left(\frac{\partial(\mu_\alpha^{\text{aq}}/T)}{\partial T}\right)_{P, x_\alpha} = -\frac{\bar{h}_\alpha^{\text{aq}}}{T^2} \quad (23)$$

Here $\alpha = \{\text{CO}_2, \text{H}_2\text{O}\}$ and represents one of the components of the mixture. Note that the partial derivative is calculated

at constant composition. In this case, the composition corresponds to that of the aqueous solution in equilibrium with the hydrate phase at T_i . $\bar{h}_\alpha^{\text{aq}}$ is the partial molar enthalpy of component α in the aqueous solution. The partial molar enthalpy is defined as,

$$\bar{h}_\alpha^{\text{aq}} = N_A \left(\frac{\partial H}{\partial N_\alpha} \right)_{P,T,N_{\beta \neq \alpha}} = \lim_{\Delta N_\alpha \rightarrow 0} N_A \left(\frac{\Delta H}{\Delta N_\alpha} \right)_{P,T,N_{\beta \neq \alpha}} \quad (24)$$

where N_A is the Avogadro's number and H is the aqueous

solution's enthalpy. The limit can be numerically evaluated computing the enthalpy for two systems that have the same number of water molecules and different number of CO_2 to evaluate the partial molar enthalpy of CO_2 . The partial molar enthalpy of water can be estimated in a similar way, i.e., the number of molecules of CO_2 in the system is kept constant while the number of water molecules changes. According to this, it is possible to evaluate the variation of the chemical potential of CO_2 and water from T_i to T_N , $\Delta\mu_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}}$ and $\Delta\mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{aq}}$, from the knowledge of the partial molar enthalpies of both components. In particular, the combination of the chemical potentials of CO_2 and water, as a function of T_N , can be obtained by integrating Eq. (23) as,

$$\frac{\mu_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}}(T_N, x_{\text{CO}_2}^N) + 5.75\mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{aq}}(T_N, x_{\text{CO}_2}^N)}{k_B T_N} = \frac{\mu_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}}(T_i, x_{\text{CO}_2}^N) + 5.75\mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{aq}}(T_i, x_{\text{CO}_2}^N)}{k_B T_i} - \int_{T_i}^{T_N} \frac{\bar{h}_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}}(T, x_{\text{CO}_2}^N) + 5.75\bar{h}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{aq}}(T, x_{\text{CO}_2}^N)}{k_B T^2} dT \quad (25)$$

Now, it is possible to find a closed expression for evaluating $\Delta\mu_N$ at arbitrary T_N and $x_{\text{CO}_2}^N$ in terms of the enthalpies of the

"hydrate", CO_2 , and water molecules. Using Eqs. (18), (21), (22), and (25), the driving force for nucleation can be written as,

$$\frac{\Delta\mu_N(T_N, x_{\text{CO}_2}^N)}{k_B T_N} = - \int_{T_i}^{T_N} \frac{h_H^H(T) - \left\{ \bar{h}_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}}(T, x_{\text{CO}_2}^N) + 5.75\bar{h}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{aq}}(T, x_{\text{CO}_2}^N) \right\}}{k_B T^2} dT \quad (26)$$

It is important to remark two important aspects of this expression. As we have previously mentioned, $\Delta\mu_N$ does not depend on the reference state. Note that the two integrations of the molar enthalpy of the "hydrate molecule" between T_{ref} and T_N , given by Eq. (18), and between T_i to T_N , given by Eq. (22), are now expressed as a single integration of the molar enthalpy of the "hydrate molecule" between T_i and T_N . In other words, since the driving force for nucleation does not depend on the reference state, the initial state of Eq. (26) is simply T_i . This is also related with another important fact: the driving force for nucleation of the hydrate is zero not only at T_3 but also along the whole solubility curve of the hydrate.

The second interesting aspect of Eq. (26) is that the integrand of the right term can be rewritten in terms of the enthalpy of dissociation of the hydrate, as $h_H^{\text{diss}} = h_H^H - (\bar{h}_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}} + 5.75\bar{h}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{aq}})$. Note that h_H^{diss} depends on T_N and $x_{\text{CO}_2}^N$. A closed expression of the driving force for nucleation can be expressed in a more compact way as,

$$\frac{\Delta\mu_N(T_N, x_{\text{CO}_2}^N)}{k_B T_N} = - \int_{T_i}^{T_N} \frac{h_H^{\text{diss}}(T, x_{\text{CO}_2}^N)}{k_B T^2} dT \quad (27)$$

Eq. (27) resembles Eq. (15) of route 3. In Eq. (27), h_H^{diss} depends on T and $x_{\text{CO}_2}^N$ and $\Delta\mu_N$ is calculated assuming ex-

plicitly that the hydrate dissociates into water and CO_2 in the aqueous solution at these conditions. However, Eq. (15) assumes that h_H^{diss} is constant and water and CO_2 dissociates into pure water and pure CO_2 .

Eq. (27) is a rigorous and exact expression (within the statistical uncertainties of the simulation results) obtained only from thermodynamic arguments for calculating the driving force for nucleation of the CO_2 hydrate at any T_N and $x_{\text{CO}_2}^N$. Obviously, this route is general and can be used to calculate driving forces for nucleation of other hydrates from the knowledge of the solubility curve of the corresponding guest with the hydrate.

Let us now to apply this route to the particular case of the CO_2 hydrate and evaluate $\Delta\mu_N^{\text{EC}}(T)$ at experimental conditions, i.e., with $x_{\text{CO}_2}^N \equiv x_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{eq}}(T)$. Each of the chemical potential changes in Eqs. (10) or (16) can be obtained evaluating the molar enthalpy of the "hydrate molecule" and the partial molar enthalpies of CO_2 and water in the aqueous solution in Eq. (26). In the case of the pure hydrate, the change in the chemical potential can be obtained performing simulations in the NPT ensemble using an anisotropic barostat, i.e., the pressure is fixed at 400 bar but each dimension of the simulation box is allowed to fluctuate independently. This ensures the absence of any stress in the equilibrated solid phase. At the beginning of each simulation, we use a cubic box formed by

FIG. 9. Schematic depiction of route 4 for obtaining $\Delta\mu_N^{\text{EC}}$. Solid curves represent the solubility curves of CO_2 in water below T_3 for CO_2 liquid-solution (green curve) and hydrate-solution (blue curve). The red squares represent hydrate-solution coexistence states at T_i , molar fraction $x_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{eq}}(P, T_i|\text{H})$ and $\mu_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}} + 5.75\mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{aq}}$ values known according to Eq. XXX. The dark yellow circles are states at a lower T , the same composition $x_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{eq}}(P, T_i|\text{H})$, and $\mu_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}} + 5.75\mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{aq}}$ values obtained from thermodynamic integration according to Eq. XX. The magenta diamond is the CO_2 liquid-solution coexistence state obtained from extrapolation from states at temperature T , composition $x_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{eq}}(P, T|L)$ and $\mu_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}}(P, T) + 5.75\mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{aq}}(P, T)$ values obtained according to Fig. 12.

27 replicas of the unit cell in a $3 \times 3 \times 3$ geometry. The dimensions of the simulation box vary between 3.85 and 3.62 nm depending on the temperature. As in the rest of simulations, we calculate the enthalpy at different temperatures, from 260 to 295 K. Simulations are run during 100 ns, 20 ns to equilibrate the system and 80 ns to calculate the molar enthalpy of the hydrate.

The changes of the chemical potentials of CO_2 and water in the aqueous solution, $\Delta\mu_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}}$ and $\Delta\mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{aq}}$, can not be performed directly according to route 4 as indicated in Fig. 8. As can be seen in Fig. 7, the solubility curve of CO_2 with the liquid phase is a convex and decreasing function of temperature. According to this, it is not possible to reach this curve from the solubility curve of CO_2 with the hydrate from a temperature T_i below T_3 following the two-steps thermodynamic path of route 4 (see also Fig. 8). A feasible solution is to choose a T_i value above T_3 . However, the T_3 of the CO_2 hydrate is located at $T_3 = 290$ K (with molar fraction $x_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{eq}}(T_3) = 0.05$), and the solubility curve with the hydrate can be only obtained up to 295 K, as it is shown in Fig. 6. This means that Eqs. (26) or (27) can be only applied to calculate $\Delta\mu_N$ for supercoolings above 270 K, approximately. It is interesting to mention that this occurs in the particular case of the CO_2 hydrate and this is not the case of the methane hydrate: Eqs. (26) or (27) can be used in a wider range of supercoolings (see the inset of Fig. 7 in this work and Fig. 4 of our previous work²⁹).

To overcome this problem, we propose to use Eqs. (26) or (27), for several values of $T_i < T_3$, and to perform an extrapo-

FIG. 10. Partial molar enthalpies of CO_2 in the aqueous solution, as a function of temperature, at different compositions: $x_{\text{CO}_2} = 0.0680$ (red circles), 0.0521 (green squares), 0.0413 (blue diamonds), 0.0335 (magenta triangles up), and 0.0215 (orange triangles down). In the inset, difference of the chemical potential of CO_2 , as a function of temperature, at the same compositions with respect to their values at the solubility curve of the hydrate at 295 (red), 290 (green), 285 (blue), 280 (magenta), and 270 K (orange) in shown.

lation/interpolation of the composition at the temperature at which we evaluate $\Delta\mu_N$, as it is indicated schematically in Fig. 9.

$\Delta\mu_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}}$ and $\Delta\mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{aq}}$, or the combination of both changes according to Eq. (25), can be obtained by performing NPT MD simulations of the solution along the 400 bar isobar at constant composition. As in the case of the “hydrate molecule”, since we are simulating bulk phases, the standard NPT is used in such a way that the three dimensions of the simulation box are allowed to fluctuate isotropically. We evaluate the partial molar enthalpies of both components at five different concentrations: $x_{\text{CO}_2} = 0.0680$, 0.0521, 0.0413, 0.0335, and 0.0215. These values are the compositions of the aqueous solution along the solubility curve of CO_2 with the hydrate, $x_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{eq}}(T_i|\text{H})$, at $T_i = 295, 290, 285, 280$, and 270, respectively. We calculate numerically the derivative of Eq. (24) by computing the enthalpy for two different systems that have the same number of water molecules and different number of CO_2 molecules and the same number of CO_2 molecules and different number of water molecules to determine $\bar{h}_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}}$ and $\bar{h}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{aq}}$, respectively. Particularly, $\bar{h}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{aq}}$ is obtained from the difference of the enthalpies of the aqueous solution using 990 and 1010 water molecules ($\Delta N_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = 20$) for all the temperatures and compositions of the mixtures. In the case of $\bar{h}_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}}$, we have used different number of CO_2 molecules depending on the composition of the mixture: 20 and 24 ($\Delta N_{\text{CO}_2} = 4$) for $x_{\text{CO}_2} = 0.0215$, 32 and 38 ($\Delta N_{\text{CO}_2} = 6$) for $x_{\text{CO}_2} = 0.0335$, 40 and 46 ($\Delta N_{\text{CO}_2} = 10$) for $x_{\text{CO}_2} = 0.0413$, 50 and 60 ($\Delta N_{\text{CO}_2} = 10$) for $x_{\text{CO}_2} = 0.0521$, and 68 and 78 ($\Delta N_{\text{CO}_2} = 10$) for $x_{\text{CO}_2} = 0.0680$. Simulations to calculate the enthalpy, at each temperature, are run during 300 ns, 50 ns

FIG. 11. Partial molar enthalpies of H_2O in the aqueous solution, as a function of temperature, at different compositions. In the inset, 5.75 times the difference of the chemical potential of H_2O , as a function of temperature, at the same compositions is shown. The symbols and colors are the same as those in Fig. 9

to equilibrate the system and 250ns as the production period. Dividing the enthalpy difference, ΔH , by the difference of the number of CO_2 molecules, ΔN_{CO_2} , and of the number of water molecules, $\Delta N_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, and multiplying by Avogadro's constant, we get estimations of $\bar{h}_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}}$ and $\bar{h}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{aq}}$ at several compositions of the mixture and temperatures.

Fig. 10 shows the partial molar enthalpy of CO_2 at five constant compositions, as functions of the temperature. The composition of the mixture in each curve corresponds to the molar fraction of the solution at several temperatures, T_i , along the solubility curve of CO_2 with the hydrate, as indicated in the previous paragraph. The difference of the chemical potential of CO_2 along the integration path (see the Fig. 8), $\Delta\mu_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}}$, is represented in the inset of Fig. 10. Note that we have five different curves, one to each temperature value T_i . We follow the same approach and represent the partial molar enthalpy of water at the same compositions in Fig. 11. In the inset is now depicted $5.75\Delta\mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{aq}}$, as function of the temperature, which represents the change of the rest of the "hydrate molecule" dissociated in the solution according to the nomenclature used in this section. As can be seen, partial molar enthalpies of CO_2 and water show small variations with the composition and decrease as the temperature decreases. The variation of both chemical potentials also exhibit similar behavior, i.e., they decrease as the temperature is lowered when keeping the composition of the mixture constant. In addition, each $\Delta\mu_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}} \rightarrow 0$ at the temperature associated with the corresponding composition on the solubility curve of CO_2 with the hydrate.

The value of $\mu_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}} + 5.75\mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{aq}}$ at a given temperature T and at the appropriate composition of the solution in equilibrium with the CO_2 liquid phase, $x_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{eq}}(P, T|L)$, can be obtained in a second step, as indicated in Fig. 9, according to the following approach. The values of $\mu_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}}$ and $5.75\mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{aq}}$, at any $T < T_3$,

FIG. 12. $\mu_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}} + 5.75\mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{aq}}$ values obtained from the route 4, as functions of composition, at 250 (red circles), 260 (green squares), 270 (blue diamonds), and 280 K (magenta triangles up). The dotted horizontal lines represent the chemical potential values of the "hydrate molecules" in the hydrate phase, the continuous lines are linear regressions of the $\mu_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}} + 5.75\mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{aq}}$ values with x_{CO_2} , and the dashed curves are the $\mu_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}} + 5.75\mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{aq}}$ values at $x_{\text{CO}_2} = 0.0215$ and assuming a variation with the composition given by Eq. (13). The composition of the solution in equilibrium with the CO_2 liquid phase using different cutoff distances r_c are represented by crosses (1.0nm) and stars (1.9nm).

are obtained using Eqs. (23) or (25), with $\alpha = \text{CO}_2$ and H_2O , and taking into account that $\mu_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}} + 5.75\mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{aq}}$ at each T_i is equal to $\mu_{\text{H}}^{\text{H}}(P, T_i)$ according to Eq.(21).

We first represent $\mu_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}} + 5.75\mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{aq}}$, as a function of composition, evaluated at several temperatures below the T_3 of the hydrate as shown in Fig. 12 (see also Fig. 9). Particularly, we have represented $\mu_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}} + 5.75\mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{aq}}$ at $T = 250, 260, 270,$ and 280 K at the compositions $x_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{eq}}$ previously selected (symbols). In addition to that, we have also represented the value of the chemical potential of the hydrate, at the four temperatures, in equilibrium with the aqueous solution along the solubility curve of the hydrate. Note that the value of $\mu_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}} + 5.75\mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{aq}}$ at 270 K is equal to that of the hydrate, $-11.2k_B T$, since it is in equilibrium with the solution with $x_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{eq}} = 0.0215$. The same is true at 280 K, i.e., $\mu_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}} + 5.75\mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{aq}} = \mu_{\text{H}}^{\text{H}} = -5.4k_B T$, state at which the solution with $x_{\text{CO}_2} = 0.0335$ is in equilibrium with the hydrate.

The values of $\mu_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}} + 5.75\mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{aq}}$, at the corresponding temperatures, follow a linear dependence with the composition of the solution. We have performed linear regressions using the five values obtained in this work, for each temperature, and the corresponding lines are also shown in Fig. 12. We have also represented the compositions of the solution in equilibrium with the CO_2 liquid phase on the solubility curve of CO_2 , $x_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{eq}}(P, T|L)$ at the four temperatures (crosses and stars). Note that these values fit in an excellent way to the linear regression. As can be seen, we have two dif-

ferent values of $x_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{eq}}(P, T|L)$ depending on the cutoff due to the dispersive interactions used, $r_c = 1.0$ (crosses) and 1.9 nm (stars). See Fig. 7 and Section III.D for further details. According to this, it is possible to know accurately the values of $\mu_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}} + 5.75 \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{aq}}$ by extrapolating/interpolating the linear fits depending on the temperature and the composition (see Fig. 12). These values, in combination with the values of $\mu_{\text{H}}^{\text{H}}(P, T)$ (already obtained in routes 1 and 2), can be used to predict with confidence the driving force for nucleation of the CO_2 hydrate using this new approach.

Before finishing this section, Fig. 12 contains valuable information that deserves to be discussed in detail. Dashed curves represent the values of $\mu_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}} + 5.75 \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{aq}}$ obtained at the lowest concentration considered, $x_{\text{CO}_2} = 0.0215$, and assuming that the variation with composition follows the approximation used in route 2 proposed by us in our previous work²⁹ and also used by Molinero and co-workers³¹ and by us in this work. In other words, the difference of the chemical potentials of CO_2 and water when the composition is varied can be calculated assuming that the activity coefficients of both component are close to 1 or are similar in the solution. Unfortunately, this approximation is not valid for CO_2 hydrates. As can be seen in Fig. 12, this approach (route 2) underestimates the value of $\mu_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}} + 5.75 \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{aq}}$ more than $0.8 k_B T$ (using $r_c = 1.0$ nm and more than $1 k_B T$ using $r_c = 1.9$ nm) at 250 K with respect to the value obtained from route 4. As we will see later in the next section, this result explains from a thermodynamic perspective why the route 2 can not be used with confidence to estimate the driving force for nucleation of the CO_2 hydrate.

5. Evaluation of $\Delta\mu_{\text{N}}^{\text{EC}}$ using different routes.

We have obtained the driving force for nucleation of the CO_2 hydrate using the four routes presented in the previous sections. All the results have been obtained using a cutoff distance for the dispersive interactions $r_c = 1.0$ nm. As we have seen in the previous sections, this value of r_c gives a dissociation temperature of the hydrate $T_3 = 290(2)$ K. The results obtained using the different routes are presented in Fig. 13. The route 1 given by Eqs. XX predicts a linear behavior of $\Delta\mu_{\text{N}}^{\text{EC}}$ with the temperature. This results is in agreement with our previous results obtained for the driving force for nucleation of the methane hydrate.²⁹

We have also used the novel route proposed in this work (route 4), based on the use of the solubility curve of CO_2 with the hydrate, given by Eqs. XXX. As we have mentioned in the previous section, the route 4 should provide reliable values of $\Delta\mu_{\text{N}}^{\text{EC}}$ since it is based on rigorous thermodynamic integration calculations. The only approximation made are the extrapolations/interpolations of the combination $\mu_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}} + 5.75 \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{aq}}$ to the $x_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{eq}}$ on the solubility curve of CO_2 with the liquid at the corresponding temperatures. However, we think this is a good approach taken into account the low values of the concentration and the results presented in Fig. 11. As can be seen in Fig. 13, small differences are seen between results obtained from routes 1 and 4. The approximations used to obtain

FIG. 13. Driving force for nucleation of the CO_2 hydrate at experimental conditions, as a function of the temperature along the 400 bar isobar with $r_c = 1.0$ nm and $T_3 = 290$ K, using the route 1 (red curve), route 2 (blue curve), route 3 (green curve), and route 4 (orange curve).

$\Delta\mu_{\text{N}}^{\text{EC}}$ via the route 1 underestimate the driving force for nucleation in nearly the whole range of temperatures considered in this work, especially in the intermediate range of temperatures.

As in our previous work,²⁹ we have also used the dissociation route (route 3) according to Eq. (15), proposed by Kashchiev and Firoozabadi.⁵⁴ The agreement between the results from route 3 and 4 is good, especially at low supercoolings. The dissociation route overestimates the values of $\Delta\mu_{\text{N}}^{\text{EC}}$ obtained from the route 4 about $0.1 k_B T$ at 260 K, approximately. This represents a value 6.5% higher than the value obtained from the route 4, the maximum difference found between both approaches in the whole range of temperatures.

Finally, we have also obtained $\Delta\mu_{\text{N}}^{\text{EC}}$, as a function of the temperature, via the route 2 proposed by us in our previous work.²⁹ This route, given by Eq. (13), entails crude approximations. As can be seen, the route 2 is not able to provide reliable predictions of $\Delta\mu_{\text{N}}^{\text{EC}}$ in the whole range of supercoolings. In fact, it overestimates its value by $0.32 k_B T$, a value 20% higher than that obtained using the more rigorous route 4 in a wide range of temperatures. This result is in agreement with the findings observed in Fig. 12 and it is a direct consequence of the main approximation made in route 2: that the activity coefficients of water and CO_2 are equal to one. Although this is a good approximation for the methane hydrate,²⁹ it is not a realistic option for the CO_2 hydrate. The root of this behavior must be found in the large differences in solubility of methane in water compared with that of CO_2 in water (in contact with both, the gas/liquid phase and the hydrate phase). See the Figs. 2 and 6 and the corresponding insets.

In summary, the route 2 is not in general a good choice for calculating driving forces for nucleation of hydrates. This

FIG. 14. Driving force for nucleation of the CO₂ hydrate at experimental conditions, as a function of the temperature along the 400 bar isobar using the route 4 with cutoff distances $r_c = 1.0$ nm (orange curve) and 1.9 nm (magenta curve).

route can be used when the solubility of guest molecules in water is extremely low. The route 3 is an easy and fast way to estimate $\Delta\mu_N^{\text{EC}}$ values. However, we do not recommend this route in general except for cases in which solubility of the guest molecules in water is extremely low, as in the case of route 2. Finally, the route 4 proposed here in the most rigorous and nearly exact way to evaluate driving forces for nucleation of hydrates.

It is important to discuss the effect of the cutoff distance due to the dispersive interactions on $\Delta\mu_N^{\text{EC}}$. We have already analyzed the effect of r_c on the solubility curve of CO₂ in contact with both, the CO₂ liquid (Fig. 2) and the hydrate (Fig. 6). Although the solubility curve of CO₂ with the hydrate is practically unaffected when r_c is changed from 1.0 to 1.9 nm, the situation is completely different for the solubility curve of CO₂ with the liquid. As a consequence of this, the T_3 of the CO₂ hydrate changes from 290(2) K when $r_c = 1.0$ nm to 292(2) K when $r_c = 1.9$ nm. Obviously, this change must also affect to the values of $\Delta\mu_N^{\text{EC}}$. We have obtained the driving force for nucleation following the route 4 using a cutoff distance $r_c = 1.9$ nm and results are compared with those using $r_c = 1.0$ nm. As can be seen in Fig. 14, the main effect is to displace the curve towards higher temperatures. This is an expected result due to the difference in the T_3 values using different cutoff distances. However, it is clearly seen that differences between both curves increases as the temperature is decreased: the difference between both values in absolute value is $0.125 k_B T$ at 290 K, approximately, but that difference increases up to $0.286 k_B T$ at 260 K, approximately. This is more than double of the value of the difference predicted at 290 K, suggesting that the increase of the cutoff distance has a deep effect on the driving force for nucleation of the system.

To check the real impact of the cutoff distance of the dis-

FIG. 15. Driving force for nucleation of the CO₂ hydrate at experimental conditions, as a function of the supercooling ΔT along the 400 bar isobar, with $r_c = 1.0$ nm (orange curve) and 1.9 nm (magenta curve) obtained using the route 4 in both cases. The driving force for nucleation of the methane hydrate along the same isobar with $r_c = 0.9$ nm is also shown (green curve).²⁹ The dissociation temperatures in each case are $T_3 = 290$ (CO₂ hydrate with $r_c = 1.0$ nm), 292 (CO₂ hydrate with $r_c = 1.9$ nm), and 295 K (methane hydrate with $r_c = 0.9$ nm).

persive interaction on the driving force for nucleation, we have plot $\Delta\mu_N^{\text{EC}}$, as a function of the supercooling ΔT , instead of the absolute temperature T . This allows to compare both results at the same supercooling and to have a clearer picture of this effect. As can be seen in Fig. 15, there is an important effect on $\Delta\mu_N^{\text{EC}}$ when r_c is changed from 1.0 to 1.9 nm. For instance, at $|\Delta T| \approx 25$ K, $\Delta\mu_N^{\text{EC}}$ changes from -1.5 to $-1.65 k_B T$ when the cutoff distance is increased. According to this, the driving force for nucleation of the hydrate is 10% lower when $r_c = 1.9$ nm than that obtained using 1.0 nm. This effect is not negligible. The origin of this displacement is due to the strong dependence of the solubility of CO₂ in water on r_c (aqueous solution in contact with the CO₂ liquid phase). Due to the effect of the cutoff distance on $\Delta\mu_N^{\text{EC}}$, appropriate values of r_c are required in order to obtain reliable values of this magnitude.

It is also very interesting to compare the driving force for the nucleation of the CO₂ and methane hydrates at the same pressure. We have determined in our previous work²⁹ the driving force at experimental conditions along the same isobar. We also present these results in Fig. 15, obtained using the route 1 and a cutoff distance of $r_c = 0.9$ nm. We compare these results with that obtained for the CO₂ hydrate using a cutoff distance of 1.0 nm. As can be seen, the driving force of the CO₂ hydrate is, in absolute value, lower than that of the methane hydrate along the isobar of 400 bar. For instance, at a supercooling of $|\Delta T| \approx 25$ K, the driving force for the methane hydrate is $\Delta\mu_N^{\text{EC}} \approx -1.7 k_B T$. At the same supercooling for the CO₂, $\Delta\mu_N^{\text{EC}} \approx -1.5 k_B T$. This means that the

driving force for the nucleation of the CO₂ hydrate, at 400 bar, is 13% lower than that of the methane hydrate at the same supercooling ($\Delta T = 25$ K). According to this, the nucleation of the methane hydrate should be more favorable than that of the CO₂ hydrate. Obviously, this would be true if the other factors that affect the nucleation rate of the hydrates are equal, i.e., the water–hydrate interfacial energy.

Finally, it is also interesting to compare the driving force for the CO₂ hydrate with that corresponding to ice Ih obtained previously by Espinosa and coworkers.⁸⁰ They have obtained a value of $\Delta\mu_N^{EC} \approx -0.29k_B T$ per water molecule considering a supercooling of 35 K at 1 bar with $r_c = 0.9$ nm. For the case of the CO₂ hydrate, the driving force is $-2.1k_B T$ per unit of hydrate molecule at the same supercooling and 400 bar. This can be transformed to give $-0.36k_B T$ per unit of water molecule. Comparing both driving forces for nucleation, the nucleation of the CO₂ hydrate is more favorable than that of the ice Ih.

The previous result is true if the other factors that affect the nucleation rate are equal or similar, particularly the interfacial free energy. The ice Ih–water interfacial free energy for the TIP4/Ice model has been recently determined by Espinosa and collaborators⁸¹ using the Mold Integration methodology. They found a value for the interfacial energy of 29.8(8) mJ/m. This value corresponds to the interfacial free energy averaged over all crystal orientations. Algaba *et al.*⁶⁴ and Zerón *et al.*⁶⁵ have also determined the CO₂ hydrate–water interfacial free energy using the Mold Integration-Host and Mold Integration-Guest. Particularly, they have found 29(2) mJ/m² and 30(2) mJ/m², respectively at 400 bar and 287 K. According to this, the nucleation of the CO₂ hydrate is more favourable than that of ice Ih since the interfacial energies of the ice and the CO₂ hydrate are similar.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we have studied the solubility of CO₂ in aqueous solutions when they are in contact via planar interfaces with a CO₂-rich liquid phase and with the hydrate phase at 400 bar using molecular dynamics computer simulations. We have also estimated the driving force for the nucleation of the CO₂ hydrate using four different routes. These properties are key to understanding, from a thermodynamics point of view, the parameters that control the nucleation of CO₂ hydrates. Water is described using the TIP4P/Ice water model and CO₂ using the TraPPE model. The unlike dispersive interactions between water and CO₂ are taken into account using the approach proposed by us several years ago. This selection allows to describe very accurately, not only the dissociation temperature of the hydrate at the pressure considered in this work, but also the CO₂ hydrate–water interfacial free energy. Calculations of solubilities have been carried out using the direct coexistence technique between two phases. Additional simulations of the pure systems, at several temperatures, have also been performed to calculate the driving force for nucleation along the isobar considered in this work.

We have analyzed the aqueous solution of CO₂ when it is

in contact with the liquid phase (pure CO₂) and with the hydrate using two different values of the cutoff associated with the dispersive interactions. From this information, we have obtained the solubility of CO₂ in water when the solution is in contact with the CO₂ liquid phase. The solubility of CO₂ decreases with temperature, in a similar way to that of methane. However, the solubility of CO₂ is one order of magnitude larger than that of methane. We also observed an important effect of the long-range dispersive interactions in the solubility curve along the isobar of 400 bar. The solubility of methane in water is also affected by these contributions but their effect is smaller. It is interesting to remark that corrections due to the long-range dispersive interactions affect in a different way both systems. Whereas the solubility of CO₂ increases with the cutoff distance, in the case of methane it decreases. This is probably an effect due to the CO₂-CO₂ and CO₂-water electrostatic interactions. We have also studied the solubility of CO₂ in the aqueous solution when it is in contact with the hydrate and analyzed its interfacial structure. This magnitude increases with the temperature, as it happens with the solubility of methane in water. Contrary to what happens when the aqueous solution is in contact with the CO₂ liquid phase, the variation of the cutoff distance due to the long-range dispersive interaction has no effect on the solubility. This behavior has been also observed in our previous study dealing with the solubility of methane in water.

The dissociation temperature of the CO₂ hydrate (T_3), at 400 bar, can be evaluated from the intersection of the two solubility curves obtained in this work. This intersection is possible because the formation of the hydrate phase, at $T < T_3$, and the formation of the CO₂ liquid phase, at $T > T_3$, are activated processes. This means that there exists metastability below and above the dissociation temperature of the hydrate at 400 bar, and because of this one can find the intersection between the two solubility curves. The temperature at which this occurs is the T_3 of the hydrate at the fixed pressure. From this analysis we find that the dissociation temperature of the hydrate is located at 290(2) K when the cutoff distance for dispersive interactions is equal to 1.0 nm. This is in good agreement (within the error bars) with our previous estimation of T_3 obtained from direct coexistence simulations and using the same cutoff distance, 287(2) K. If the cutoff distance is larger (1.9 nm), the T_3 is located at 292(2) K. Although the value obtained in this work for a cutoff distance of 1.0 nm compares well with our previous estimation, 287(2) K (within the error bars), it is possible that finite-size effects produce a shift of T_3 towards higher temperatures, as well as the value used to account for the long-range dispersive interactions.

We also estimate the driving force for nucleation of the CO₂ hydrate in this preliminary study of the thermodynamic parameters that determine the nucleation. Particularly, we have calculated $\Delta\mu_N$ using the three routes proposed in our paper (routes 1-3). Since the solubility of CO₂ in water is higher than that of methane by one order of magnitude, we have proposed a novel and alternative route based on the use of the solubility curve of CO₂ with the hydrate. This new route (which we refer to as route 4 in this paper) considers rigorously the non-ideality of the aqueous solution of CO₂ and provides reliable

results for $\Delta\mu_N$. Routes 1, 3, and 4 provide similar values of the driving force for nucleation of the CO₂ hydrate in a wide range of supercoolings. Unfortunately, the route 2 can not be used for CO₂ hydrates due to the non-ideality of the water + CO₂ mixture at the conditions considered.

The driving force for nucleation of the CO₂ hydrate obtained in this work using the novel route 4 is $\Delta\mu_N \approx -0.36k_B T$ (per water molecule) at 400 bar and a supercooling of 35 K. This value lies below (is more negative) the driving force for nucleation of ice Ih at 1 bar and the same supercooling, $\Delta\mu_N \approx -0.29k_B T$ (also per water molecule). Since other factors that affect to the nucleation rate are similar (i.e., the interfacial free energy), our results indicates that CO₂ hydrates nucleate more easily than ice Ih. However, should be taken into account that this comparison is not straightforward since CO₂ is needed for the formation of the CO₂ hydrate, but not for the ice.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was financed by Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación (Grant No. PID2021-125081NB-I00), Junta de Andalucía (P20-00363), and Universidad de Huelva (P.O. FEDER UHU-1255522 and FEDER-UHU-202034), all four cofinanced by EU FEDER funds. We also acknowledge the Centro de Supercomputación de Galicia (CESGA, Santiago de Compostela, Spain) for providing access to computing facilities. The authors also acknowledge Project No. PID2019-105898GB-C21 of the Ministerio de Educación y Cultura. We also acknowledge access to supercomputer time from RES from project FI-2022-1-0019. J. G. acknowledges the national support from Gdansk University of Technology by the DEC-09/2021/IDUB/II.1/AMERICIUM/ZD grant under the AMERICIUM - "Excellence Initiative - Research University" program. Part of the computations were carried out at the Centre of Informatics Tricity Academic Supercomputer & Network. The research was supported in part by PL-Grid Infrastructure.

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